

REScoopVPP - a community-driven virtual power plant that provides flexibility services to the grid

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Abstract – By 2050, 98 million Europeans could become prosumers by joining an energy community. The Horizon 2020 project REScoopVPP brings together partners from different energy communities to develop a community-driven smart building ecosystem to support energy services for aggregators, energy service companies (ESCOs), balance responsible parties (BRPs) and renewable suppliers. The ecosystem consists of a Community-driven Flexibility Box (COFY-Box) acting as a smart home controller, plus a set of community tools that will enable energy communities to become real-time asset operators.

One of the unique features of this project is that the focus is on the energy cooperative's perspective and its evolving role as a market actor, either as an energy service provider, aggregator, electricity supplier, BRP or power plant operator. The business models and use cases will also target the perspective of the end-user or homeowner. The output of this work, supported by the technical requirements and KPIs, will be a key element for the development and large-scale implementation in Belgium, France, Germany, Spain and the UK. Additionally, a set of optimization algorithms for DR aggregators or suppliers will be proposed to help cooperatives understand the best strategy for their specific portfolio and the value of their available flexibility.

Keywords: prosumers; energy community; aggregator; energy service company; energy supplier; cooperative; end-user; business models; optimization; demand response; flexibility

1 INTRODUCTION

On 30 November 2016, the European Commission introduced the ‘Clean Energy for all Europeans Package’ (CEP), for which one of the goals was placing the consumer at the heart of the energy transition. This was realized for instance by recognising for the first time under EU law the rights of citizens and communities to engage directly in the energy sector [1][2].

Overall, citizens and energy communities can play a key role in facilitating the decentralisation of the energy system and the integration of distributed renewable energy sources [3]. But their long-term success will depend on their ability to operate energy networks in a cost-efficient way, bringing benefits for their members and across the whole energy system. One way energy communities can achieve this is by implementing strategies for local optimisation of production and consumption energy assets. While there are multiple ways to achieve this, in this paper we will focus on demand-side flexibility, or demand-response (DR).

Demand response can be provided by shifting demand - in time or amount - to help match supply. According to IRENA [4], demand-side flexibility can be defined as a portion of the demand, including that coming from the electrification of other energy sectors (i.e., heat or transport via sector coupling), that could be reduced, increased or shifted in a specific period of time to:

- 1) facilitate the integration of variable renewable energy by reshaping load profiles to match its generation,
- 2) reduce peak load and seasonality, and
- 3) reduce electricity generation costs by shifting load from periods with a high price of supply to periods with lower prices.

Unleashing the flexibility potential on the demand side has become an attractive option for many energy communities’ business models, either directly or indirectly. It can be used to increase (collective) self-consumption of locally produced electricity or from a supplier’s portfolio; it can be used to decrease electricity costs by shifting consumption according to spot markets and even to reduce grid costs, for example by reducing their (collective) connection capacity. In addition, there is potential for energy communities to generate revenue through participation in flexibility mechanisms such as ancillary services [5].

In that context, the REScoop VPP project focuses on the development and testing of necessary digital tools in five countries to maintain the balance between generation and consumption, within the community and outside. The tools also focus on making existing buildings smarter by developing technologies to use devices like heat pumps, domestic hot water, solar panels, electric vehicles and home batteries already present in homes and other buildings more efficiently. With these tools, citizens are able to take part in several energy services. By aligning their energy consumption to the availability of energy production, citizens actively contribute to the shift of the energy system from a centralised fossil fuel-based system to a decentralised renewable one, meanwhile gaining control over their energy bill.

2 RESCOOPVPP: PROJECT OVERVIEW AND GOALS

One of the main goals of the projects is to facilitate the implementation of demand response (DR), virtual power plants (VPPs) and more generally to build a flexible community able to maximise the consumption of renewable energy sources (RES) [6]. The strategy to achieve this is to develop and implement community tools in large-scale experimentation in Belgium, France, Germany, Spain and the UK. The project will demonstrate the potential of energy communities to become real-time asset operators, acting as suppliers or aggregators, in the provision of flexibility and optimisation services such as the promotion of self-consumption, should it be at the individual or collective level.

Each test country in this project has a ‘REScoop’ (Renewable Energy Sources Cooperative) as a pilot site leader that coordinates the testing of the REScoopVPP tools in the respective country. Even though the conditions and priorities of each pilot site are different, there are a set of goals that are common across locations (Table 1).

Table 1: Pilot site common goals overview

	Description
<i>Engaging prosumers with flexible assets and test potential optimisation services</i>	These possible future services will strengthen the current business models of cooperatives, either as suppliers or aggregators.
<i>Test and improve forecasting algorithms</i>	These algorithms will enable reducing portfolio imbalance costs and therefore lower the energy bills of its customers.

Increased engagement and awareness of end-users without compromising comfort	REScoopVPP monitoring tools will trigger energy savings through energy efficiency and rational energy use. This will be achieved for instance by providing them with monitoring services and insights related to self-consumption, through an energy Monitoring dashboard.
Co-develop flexibility tools with other cooperatives	At the end of the project, the objective is to found a European entity proposing REScoopVPP tools and services through an attractive offer for energy cooperatives in Europe. This EU cooperative is called the COFY Company. By being involved in the co-development process, the cooperatives responsible for the pilot sites can potentially keep the ownership of the solution created in the project.

The project will propose community-driven flexibility (COFY) smart box concept with an open architecture and a set of community applications in seamless cooperation with it to provide forecasting, dynamic pricing and OpenADR. An overview of REScoopVPP architecture is presented in the diagram below. It highlights the three functional levels of operation and general infrastructure. These are legacy equipment controls, local control units (COFY-box) and Community tools as shown in the figure below [7].

Figure 1: REScoopVPP architecture overview.

From the technical perspective, REScoopVPP aims at delivering a modular solution based on a set of products. The product architecture involves five key parts, as seen in Figure 2: the COFY-Box, the COFY-Cloud, the end user’s Energy Monitoring Application, The Community Virtual Power Plant Dashboard and the Supplier/BRPs Forecasting Tools.

Figure 2: Product architecture.

The implementation of such tools is expected to bring added value to the actors involved in the service implementation, from social and environmental benefits to new business opportunities. The next chapter provides an overview of the business models identified for this project.

3 BUSINESS MODELS FOR ENERGY COOPERATIVES

From the descriptions presented above, we can already recognise a diversity of purposes, governance models, sizes, and owned assets. Just like energy communities, cooperatives can and do perform activities across the energy sector. Although most cooperatives engage in RES generation activities, the falling feed-in-premiums for RES generation have motivated cooperatives to extend their scope and look into other energy-related activities [8], such as (collective) self-consumption optimisation.

In parallel, the gradual digitalisation and decentralisation of the energy system are both pressuring system operators to handle uncertainty and variability and opening paths for new market actors to help them do it. In this context, REScoopVPP sets out to explore and test innovative business models for energy cooperatives and their members, and understand the nuances of economic, technical and social viability according to the type of organization.

The pilot partners worked collaboratively to develop the concept of the most relevant business models for their implementation sites. The list of all business models, with the provider role for the executing cooperative, the receivers and the short description can be found in

Table 2. Through this framework, the value of each business model is defined through the activities or interactions between the actors and the value they provide for the entire system. The value created is defined in economic terms, through costs and revenues. In total, twelve business models have been described in detail, including the user-friendliness and a financing, deployment and exploitation strategy for the implementation countries, building on the respective market circumstances.

Table 2: Business models overview.

Nr.	Summary	Provider Role	Receivers
BM1	This business model describes the activity of a cooperative controlling domestic equipment independently from any retail contract, in order to provide services at grid level i.e. balancing consumption and production or avoiding congestion.	Aggregator or BRP	End-user, DSO/TSO
BM2	This business model addresses the activities of a BRP/Supplier using REScoopVPP tools to shift its customers' demand to respond to dynamic time-of-use tariffs. Supply costs decrease by helping the purchase of power at lower market prices.	BRP or Supplier	End-user, Power market/External BRP

BM3a	This business model addresses the activities of a supplier using REScoopVPP forecasting tools to improve offtake and injection forecasts of its portfolio, thereby reducing its imbalance costs. It is the precondition for Business Model 3b.	Supplier	Forecast provider, Market access provider, Power market
BM3b	This business model addresses the activities of a BRP/Supplier using REScoopVPP tools to shift its customers' demand by using their response to a demand response signal, to increase the real-time consumption of local production and to decrease imbalances. The precondition is Business Model 3a.	BRP or Supplier	End-user, Power market/External BRP
BM4	This business model addresses the activities of a supplier offering energy monitoring services through the use of a COFY-Box and of a dashboard for the end-user. This service may be sold for a fee or as a means to improve customer retention.	Supplier	End-user, ESCo
BM5	This business model addresses the activities of a supplier offering energy monitoring services using the dashboard for the end-user without the COFY-Box. This service may be sold for a fee or as a means to improve customer retention.	Supplier	End-user, ESCo
BM6	This business model describes the activities of an Energy Service Company or of a supplier using REScoopVPP tools to propose energy efficiency services using Energy Performance Contracting, where the service is retributed based on the savings performed.	ESCo or Supplier	End-user
BM7	This business model describes the activities of a supplier using REScoopVPP tools to increase self-consumption in the context of the Mieterstrom regulation in place in Germany, allowing special tariffs in a multi-tenant building.	Supplier	Power plant owner, Building owner, End-user
BM8	This business model describes the activities of a supplier using REScoopVPP tools to increase self-consumption in the context of the collective self-consumption regulation in place in Spain, allowing collective self-consumption in a multi-tenant building or a defined perimeter.	Supplier or ESCo	Power plant owner, End-user
BM9	This business model describes the activities of a power plant owner or of an Energy Service Company using REScoopVPP tools to increase individual self-consumption.	Power plant owner or ESCo	End-user
BM10	This business model description explores the set-up of an EU cooperative as a digital services provider. The case where the COFY Company is a digital AND energy service provider is explored in Business Model 11.	COFY Company	Member-Coop, End-user
BM11	This business model covers the activities, costs and revenues of a future EU cooperative entity selling the REScoopVPP tools together with new energy services. However, in the absence of a single energy market at the EU level, the proposal is for the EU cooperative to work in partnership with some national cooperatives to fulfill the role of national branches.	COFY Company	National BRP-coop, Local coop

As highlighted in BM1, BM2, BM3, BM7, BM8 and BM9, the pilot partners are interested in exploring business models that make use of the demand-side flexibility unlocked through the implementation of the COFY-boxes and the rest of the technologies. As part of the project, the different strategies available for cooperatives to make use of this flexibility will be explored and simulated.

4 VARIOUS TRADING STRATEGIES FOR ENERGY COOPERATIVES ACCORDING TO DIFFERENT ROLES

Active demand and supply at the prosumer level - flexible loads, controllable local generation units and local storage units - can offer flexibility by allowing their load or generation profiles to be purposely changed from the planned, or normal, generation or consumption pattern. The trigger to this change is usually a demand response incentive, which can either be implicit or explicit.

According to USEF, in implicit demand-response, prosumers exposed to dynamic energy or grid tariffs (e.g. Time-of-Use tariffs) can reduce their energy bills by shifting (manually or automatically) their load and/or generation to periods with low energy or grid prices. On the other hand, when subscribed to an explicit demand-response mechanism, a prosumer sees flexibility directly exposed to energy markets and ancillary products. Prosumers receive (financial) rewards for agreeing to respond to an aggregator's request to adjust their load or generation profile.

Flexibility on the demand-side is where we find the highest complexity since it resides on the retail side of the market, often with no direct access to wholesale and balancing markets [9]. In the context of this project, the different strategies available for cooperatives to manage their portfolio of customers and producers and create value from it will be studied. In particular, simulations for these strategies will help clarify the grid and market impact of implementing such strategies on a larger scale.

In this section, we will present:

- a) a list of different strategies that are available for the end-user upon installation of the COFY-box and connection of controllable loads,
- b) potential optimisation strategies for cooperatives to make use of that newly available flexibility.
- c) It should be noted that the strategies provided are limited to the scope of the use cases and business models chosen for this project.

4.1. END-USER PERSPECTIVE

By joining an energy cooperative, end users can take part in the transition towards a fully decarbonised energy system by 2050 by collectively investing in their renewable power plants, by increasing the flexibility in demand-response schemes and by obtaining more decision-making power over their energy usage patterns. By having COFY-boxes installed in residential homes and other buildings, the end-users will have access to multiple control strategies, which can be identified as implicit DR, namely 1) self-consumption and self-sufficiency optimisation, 2) off-take capacity optimisation and 3) dynamic pricing optimisation. In addition, the end-user may opt to 4) enrol its COFY-box in an explicit DR programme through user registration/opt-in. In this scenario, the end-user may respond to flexibility requests from an aggregator in return for revenue.

In general, the motivation for the end-user to subscribe to either one of these strategies would be to either maximise energy savings or increase revenue from flexibility provision. And while there are also benefits for the entities providing these options (which in this case would be the cooperatives), it is also true that more decisional power given to the end-user can lead to uncertainty for the cooperative managing their profiles.

4.2. COOPERATIVE PERSPECTIVE

By having access to end-users data through the COFY-box readings, as well as forecasts for portfolio consumption and production, and the ability to send signals and flexibility requests, cooperatives are better positioned to deliver an additional set of services and hence improve their business model and value provided to the members. This includes lowering operating/balancing costs in the role of supplier and producer (which can result in lower energy bills for the customers) or add value to current services. On the other hand, a supplier acting as an aggregator can easily bring residential flexibility to energy-only markets, either implicitly (through dynamic price contracts) or explicitly (by dispatching the flexibility in its portfolio). The supplier has a good knowledge of the customer consumption habits. This is, however, more complicated for an independent aggregator. The options for an independent aggregator are limited and depend on several aspects, i.e., the type of supply contract of the customer, the allocation method for this customer and the baseline requirements. Indeed, the aggregator needs to know precisely the type of appliances used by the DR participants to be able to control them. There are also lots of challenges linked to data security and personal integrity. As the retailer has already access to the customers' data, an aggregator-retailer would be easier to implement [10].

Through the use of DR incentives shared through the project tools, cooperatives can make use of the available flexibility from end-users to:

- Create new revenue streams from service provision: such as self-consumption optimisation, or peak absorption for reduced off-take capacity (1, 2)

- Decrease supply costs: purchasing (external) power at lower market prices by shifting demand through offering dynamic time-of-use tariffs (3)
 - Increase real-time consumption of portfolio production: by sending DR signals that motivate a shift in consumer demand to follow portfolio's produced electricity (4)
- Increase revenue from flexibility sold on ancillary markets: maximise the value of aggregated flexibility through explicit DR to sell it as ancillary services (4)

Some of the technical requirements for these strategies include a local, quasi-real-time optimisation engine, local energy measurements (PV inverter and digital meter) besides forecasts of PV production and domestic energy use. A brief overview of the mentioned strategies with a listing of main pros and cons for end-user and cooperative is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Demand-response strategies, and respective benefits for end-users and cooperatives.

Control Strategy	Benefits for end-user	Benefits for cooperative
<i>1) Self-consumption and self-sufficiency optimisation</i>	- Reducing energy bill for end-user	- Potential fee for supplier for service provided
<i>2) Off-take capacity optimisation</i>	- Reducing energy bill (capacity tariff cost) for end-user	- Potential fee for supplier for service provided
<i>3) Dynamic pricing optimisation</i>	- Reducing energy bill for end-user	- Decrease supply costs by purchasing (external) power at lower market prices
<i>4) Explicit DR programme</i>	- Revenue for participation in explicit DSR programmes either indirectly (under service contract) or direct payment	Depending on the goal: - Reduce portfolio balance costs, in particular for suppliers that pay producers at a fixed rate, reduces their exposure to market prices - Increase the use of variable production from its portfolio. - Receive payment from DSO/TSO for delivered flexibility

5 CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

The REScoopVPP project focuses on the development and testing of necessary digital tools in five countries to maintain the portfolio balance between production and demand. With these tools, citizens are empowered and enabled to take part in several energy services that result in economic benefits. To control these devices, a community-driven flexibility box will be installed in people's homes and other buildings.

In those countries, tests of the REScoopVPP tools will be conducted and eleven business models will be explored. Each country has a REScoop (Renewable Energy Sources Cooperative) as pilot site leader that coordinates the testing of the REScoopVPP tools with citizens in their respective country. Beyond testing the viability of the technical tools developed throughout this project, the pilot partners intend to test how these tools can help them provide new services to their members and improve their current business model.

In the context of demand-side flexibility optimisation strategies, the next steps include gathering all the relevant data available from the pilot sites to perform the simulations and identifying the best pricing strategy for each scenario simulated. The results will ideally help cooperatives of this project, and potentially more thorough results 'dissemination, understand the best strategy to make use of their portfolios' flexible assets and with that improve their business case and value provided to their members and overall energy system.

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6 REFERENCES

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